

Comparison of the expression of SARS-CoV-2 receptors in in vitro skin and lung models

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Abstract

The outbreak of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) has caused the pandemic associated with the severe acute pulmonary disease named COVID-19 (coronavirus disease 2019). The exact pathogenesis of severe COVID-19 remains unclear, but it typically involves a hyperinflammatory response following viral infection and induces significant damage in the respiratory tract.

The recommended hygiene procedures for the fight against COVID-19 include repeated handwashing and frequent use of hand sanitizer that can disrupt the skin barrier integrity. Loss of skin barrier integrity represents a potential transmission route for SARS-CoV-2 through the skin.

The entry of SARS-CoV-2 in host cells depends on the availability of virus receptors and entry cofactors on the surface of host cells. The most important receptors identified so far are the Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor, the transmembrane serine protease 2 (TMPRSS2), and the Neuropilin-1 (NRP-1), all three receptors are under the control of the Androgen Receptor (AR).

In this talk, we will present the constitutive expression of SARS-CoV-2 key receptors; ACE2, TMPRSS2, NRP1, and AR in primary culture of human epidermal keratinocytes and human dermal fibroblasts, in 3D-reconstructed human epidermis model and in human skin biopsies. Comparison will be made with Calu-3 cell line and 3D-EpiAirway model, representing lung models. Moreover, the effect of stimulation with lipopolysaccharide (inflammatory agent) on the modulation of mRNA expression of cytokines markers and SARS-CoV-2 receptors will be measured and compared in the in vitro skin and lung models.